

A STUDY ON LEVEL OF AWARENESS AMONG MALE TEACHER TOWARDS RTE ACT 2009 AT MURSHIDABD DISTRICT IN WEST BENGAL

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Introduction:

"Every child between the ages of 6 to 14 years has the right to free and compulsory education: Everybody has the right to education. Education shall be free at least in the elementary and fundamental stages. Elementary education shall be compulsory"

.....86th Constitution Amendment Act via Article 21A

Education is a human right and an essential tool for achieving the goals of equality, development and peace. Non-discriminatory education benefits both girls and boys and thus ultimately contributes to more equal relationships between women and men. Equality of access to and attainment of educational qualifications is necessary if more women are to become agents of change. On a regional level, girls and boys have achieved equal access to primary education, except in some parts of West Bengal. Particularly the primary school years are an important phase in child's education because it is the foundation for his learning. It is also the time when the children are most inquisitive- what do they ask and how their questions are answered will be crucial to his development later on in life. During these formative year, the education should build their confidence and desire in learn and expose them to different aspects of learning, in academic and non- academic areas, so that the children will have a well-rounded primary education. It is very essential that every section of the society is able to access the quality education.

The basic primary education underpins the success of society. Every year of primary education increases a person's productivity and reduces their dependence on social resources. The goal of education is to enable children to learn, realize their full potential and participate meaningfully in society. In spite of increasing enrolment rates, too many children are learning far less than what they are taught about and what they ought to learn in school. This low learning achievement is most frequently due to combination of factors that include inadequate learning environments, inappropriate teaching method, frequently unmotivated teachers and malnourishment and ill- health of children themselves. Progress has been made in elementary education, where equal access of girls and boys has been achieved in some countries. Enrolment of girls and women in tertiary education has increased considerably. In many districts, elementary female teachers have also played an important complementary role in improving access to education at all levels. Yet more than seven years before the Right to Education Act 2009 were lunched and the Framework for Action to Education for All. India's Constitution guarantees free primary school education for both boys and girls up to age 14.

Statement of the Problem:

The present researcher has taken up the present descriptive study entitled as "A Study on Level of Awareness among Male Teacher towards RTE Act 2009 at Murshidabad District in West Bengal".

Need and Significance of the Study:

In this context the present researcher has taken significance as follows:

- The present study has helped to know the awareness of male teacher of elementary Schools towards the RTE Act, 2009 in the district of Murshidabad , West Bengal.
- This study has been find out strategic plans of action prepared for providing Universal Elementary Education (UEE) and Sarba Siksha Abhiyan (SSA) to implement RTE, Act 2009..
- It has been helped to increase the standard of education in Murshidabad District, Right to Education Act is more essential for the betterment of education of a nation.
- This study has helped the male teacher to emphasis on those influential factors which are positive for the teacher's positive attitude about the RTE Act 2009.
- The study like this will be relevant to the field of higher education.
- This study will grow more interest among the male teachers towards RTE Act 2009.
- Further this study will help us to understand the significant difference of awareness of RTE Act among the male and female primary school teachers.

Review of Related Literature:

- **Fathima Jaseena (2011):**

Study has conducted "A study on Right to Education among Awareness of M.Ed Trainees" to find out the awareness of M.Ed students about right to education and to study the effect of gender and type of management

of the institution on the awareness of Right to Education Act, 2009. The findings of the study reveal that male M.Ed students possess significantly higher awareness about the Right to Education Act, 2009 than the female M.Ed students. And the management of the M.Ed College does not effect on the awareness of the Right to Education Act, 2009.

- **K. Prem lakshmi (2011):**

Study has conducted a study on “Right to Education and Common School System-Perception among Teachers” to study the opinion about Common School System from School Teachers of Government and Matriculation Schools. The findings of the study reveal that there is a significant difference in perceptions between male and female teachers towards Common School System. And also found that there is no significant difference in perception between Urban and Rural school teachers towards Common School System.

- **Niradhar Dey & Binod Beck (2011):**

Study have conducted a study on “The Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act 2009: Teachers Perception” to study the awareness and opinion of teachers towards the Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009. The findings of the study reveal that in most of the cases it was observed that the senior teachers were less aware about the RTE Act, 2009. Senior teachers were not interested to materialize the Act by heart and hand. Though the junior teachers were little bit more ahead than seniors still then it was not impressive and satisfactory. It was also found that most of the teachers were not in favour of prohibition of admission test and fail system in elementary education.

- **Meghana Kumar (2012):**

Studied the problems of implementation of the Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act 2009 (the “Act” or “RTE”) with a particular focus on the grievance redressed process or mechanisms set out in the Act designed to get children that are out of school, into education. To do this, the study focuses on one specific area in Delhi, namely a slum pocket called Zakhira in Karolbagh zone, one of the 12 zones into which Delhi has been divided by the Municipal Corporation of Delhi for the purposes of administering the city.

Objectives of the Study:

The objectives of the present study are as follows:

- To study the level of awareness among elementary school male teachers towards RTE, Act. 2009.
- To study whether the rural and urban primary school male teachers “ having high and low levels of awareness towards Right to Education Act 2009 differ significantly.
- To study whether the government and private primary school male teachers“ having High and Low levels of awareness towards Right to Education Act 2009 differ significantly.
- To study whether the trained and non trained primary school male teachers“ having High and Low levels of awareness towards Right to Education Act 2009 differ significantly.

Hypothesis of the Study:

Based on the above objectives of the study the following three major null hypotheses have been formulated.

OH₁: There is no significant difference between the levels of awareness of urban and rural elementary male teachers towards RTE, Act. 2009.

OH₂: There is no significant difference between the levels of awareness of Government and Private school male teachers towards RTE, Act. 2009.

OH₃: There is no significant difference between the levels of awareness of experience trained and experience non trained male teachers towards RTE, Act. 2009.

Determiners of the Study:

Determiners of the study mean the items which are aware elementary male teachers of RTE, Act 2009. The determiners which are found depending on the subject are as follows:

- Information relating to School Infrastructure.
- Information relating to Free and Compulsory education.
- Information relating to Sarba Siksha abhiyan (SSA)
- Information relating to Teacher facilities.
- Information about the Curriculum.

Delimitation of the Study:

The Present study has been delimited to the following extent:

- The researcher has been chosen only male teachers of elementary level as sample.
- The researcher has been chosen only 60 Samples.
- The researcher has been carrying forward his research only at Murshidabad District in West Bengal (India).
- The study has done only 8 schools in West Bengal only.
- The sample has been chosen only from Government & Private school Murshidabad District.
- The study has been taken from both rural and urban area of Murshidabad District.

Methodology:

Nature of the study	Descriptive study (Present oriented study) one kind of Normativesurvey studies.
Variables	Male Teacher’s awareness of Elementary educational Level. Male Teacher’s awareness of different factors of RTE Act2009. Dependent variables Right to Education Act-2009. Universalization of Elementary Education (UEE).Sarba Siksha Abhiyan (SSA) Independent variables Location of schools: Rural & Urban. Type of management of schools: Government & Private. Educational Qualifications of the primary school teachers: Trained& Non trained. Demographic variables
Population	The teachers of eight elementary and upper elementary schools under Murshidabad District (West Bengal).
Sample	60 teachers (Male) of eight elementary schools have selectedrandomly. (Random sampling method)
Sampling techniques	Probability sample technique has been used in this study.
Tools used	Formulate one English version questioner. (Quantitive & Qualitative both) One kind of awareness scale. Questions/Item number-40. Measure options with the three point scale. (“Agree” (A), "More orLess Agree" (MA/ LA), Disagree (DA) Time – 60 Minutes
Collection of Data (Tools)	The researcher visited the randomly selected schools and the scalewas administered to selected teachers for data collection.
Scoring Procedure	A score of '3', '2', '1' are given to the responses of the sample in thegiven order for the favorable statements and they are reversed for the unfavorable statements. The grant score has used to interpret theoverall awareness of the teachers.
Statistical Techniques	Collection of Data (Score) has analysis by using statistical techniques like Mean, SD (Standard Deviation), t-test, Percentage Ranking, Graphical representation – Bar graph.
Validity & Reliability	The check list score has a high content and constructed validity as expressed by three experts of psychology and then the scale has beenapplied to teachers. The‘t’ value for the scale has found to be significant at 0.01 level. Test retest reliability method apply Result = +0.93 (Very highly positive co-relation)

Analysis and Interpretation of Data:

In this study the researcher collected data from the 60 Elementary school male teachers in Murshidabad District of West Bengal. All the data are collect by questionnaire. The collected data will of no meaning, if it would not put on the process of analysis and interpretation. Simply, from the raw data it will not possible to bring any kind of inference. Keeping in view the objectives of the study and their corresponding hypothesis, the data has been statistically processed using appropriate design and technique. There are three hypothesis regarding awareness of Right to Education Act among the elementary school male teachers. All the hypotheses are analyzed individually. The awareness of Right to Education Act is understood using Mean, S.D, t-test. All the hypotheses are analyzed and interpreted under each category. Besides all the results have compared between the categories.

Testing of the Hypothesis:

OH₁: There exists no significant difference between the levels of awareness of urban male andrural male teachers towards RTE, Act. 2009.

After observing the checklists of the total number of sample (60 samples of them 30 Urban male and 30 Rural male) then a descriptive table and a bar graph were prepared to make the conception clear in respect of percentile.

Table 1: Mean, SD and ‘t’- Ratio showing difference in RTE awareness among Urban maleand Rural male Elementary Teachers

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	S.D	Mean-Difference	df	t-value	Levels of Significant
Locality	Urban male	30	73.53	12.02	3.12	58	1.07	Significant
	Rural male	30	69.02	9.35				

Figure 1: Bar graph of Mean distribution showing difference in RTE awareness amongUrban male and Rural male Elementary Teachers.

OH₂: There exists no significant difference between the levels of awareness of Government school male teachers and Private school male teachers towards RTE, Act. 2009.

After observing the checklists of the total number of sample (60 samples of them 44 Government male and 16 Private male) then a descriptive table and a bar graph were prepared to make the conception clear in respect of percentile.

Table 2: Mean, SD and 't'- Ratio showing difference in RTE awareness among Governmentmale and Private male Elementary Teachers

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	S.D	Mean-Difference	df	t- value	Levels of Significant
Types of School	Government male	44	71.36	11.16	2.62	58	2.30	Significant
	Privatemale	16	69.07	10.21				

Figure 2: Bar graph of Mean distribution showing difference in RTE awareness amongGovernment male and Private male Elementary Teachers

OH₃: There exists no significant difference between the levels of awareness of experience trained male teachers and experience non trained male teachers towards RTE, Act. 2009.

After observing the checklists of the total number of sample (60 samples of them 39 Trained male and 21 non trained male) then a descriptive table and a bar graph were prepared to make the conception clear in respect of percentile.

Table 3: Mean, S.D. and 't'- Ratio showing difference in RTE awareness among Trained maleand non trained male Elementary Teachers

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	S.D	Mean-Difference	df	t-value	Levels of Significant
Training Experience	Trained Male	39	71.02	10.32	4.01	58	1.51	Significant
	Non Trained Male	21	64.82	8.27				

Figure 3: Bar graph of Mean distribution showing difference in RTE awareness among Trained male and non trained male Elementary Teachers.

Major Findings of the Study:

The major findings of this study are reported here. A section of this chapter also points out the limitations of the present work in order to overcome these limitations and arrive at more comprehensive and more reliable result; some suggestions for further research have been made. **OH₁**: Observation of Table 1 reveals that Mean and S.D values of Urban male and Rural male teachers is 73.53, 69.02 and 12.02, 9.35. Calculated t-value is 1.07 which is significant at 0.05 level. Hence the calculated t-value is less than the table t-value. Hence Null Hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis accepted. It means that Urban male and Rural male Elementary Teachers have different awareness. It is therefore, concluded that there is significant difference in RTE Act,2009 awareness among Urban male and Rural male Elementary Teachers.

OH₂: Observation of Table 1 reveals that Mean and S.D values of Government male and Private male teachers is 71.36, 69.07 and 11.16, 10.21. Calculated t-value is 2.30 which is significant at 0.05 level. Hence the calculated t-value is greater than the table t-value. Hence Null Hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis accepted. It means that Government male and Private male Elementary Teachers have different awareness. It is therefore, concluded that there is significant difference in RTE Act,2009 awareness among Government male and Private male Elementary Teachers.

OH₃: Observation of Table 1 reveals that Mean and S.D values of trained male and non trained male teachers is 71.02, 64.82 and 10.32, 8.27. Calculated t-value is 1.51 which is significant at 0.05 levels. Hence the calculated t-value is less than the table t-value. Hence Null Hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis accepted. It means that trained male and non trained male Elementary Teachers have equal awareness. It is therefore, concluded that there is significant difference in RTE Act,2009 awareness among Trained male and non trained male Elementary Teachers.

Educational Implication:

- It will serve as basic data for the research scholars who are conducting research related to RTE Act, 2009. It will serve as guides to principal, administrators in creating awareness which is very important for implementation of RTE.
- It will show that male teachers are more aware than female teachers towards RTE. So, the government should organize seminars, in-service teacher training programmes (workshop, refresher course) for female teachers in order to generate awareness. There is strong need of teacher training program on right to education act. This can be undertaken through mass awareness programmes as well as ensuring proper understanding by stakeholders responsible for its implementation.
- Educational planners serve as basis for planning different programmes for creating awareness among male teachers. Education department should provide more study leaves so that teachers can participate and get more information about RTE for attending awareness programmes. This can be done through mass awareness programmes.
- The RTE Act cannot be properly implemented without the awareness of parents. Orientation programmes for parents and guardians should also be arranged at different levels. When the parents will be aware of their rights, they would avail the services and opportunities provided under RTE Act.
- School authorities should also organize different orientation programmes, workshops and seminars for giving knowledge of provisions and features of RTE act to teachers. And by acquiring the knowledge about RTE the teachers may be made able to contribute towards the fulfilment of the goal of

compulsory and free education.

Conclusion:

Our country is facing multitude of problems mainly because many citizens are not educated. They are unable to read and write even. In such a situation, they do not get access to much information that is available. Therefore, Right to Education Act was enacted in the parliament for providing free and compulsory elementary education to all children between the ages of four to sixteen who are going to be the responsible citizen of the country in future. Government has enacted and implemented the Act in a right spirit. This is not the responsibility of the government only. Everybody in the country should take this as a challenge and help the government in the successful implementation of the Act across the country. Whenever someone comes across with children who are not enrolled and their parents, he should encourage and propagate the purpose behind the Act and the benefit a child and his family get out of it. Every community member should come out of the shell and voluntarily help in implementing the RTE Act directly or indirectly.

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